

Research

Dissecting the complexities of education policy reform for results: Does size really matter?

A comparative analysis of vocational education policy reform of the largest system and the smallest: A case of China and Lesotho

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Abstract: Often referred to as the manufacturing hub of the world, China shares significant features with other developing nations in terms of its quest to lead in labor intensive manufacturing, a policy embedded within its education system. It is against this backdrop that this comparative study is undertaken, contrasting policy development and implementation between the two systems that share similar goals of leading labor intensive manufacturing. We therefore review vocational education reform processes in both China and Lesotho, and take stock of each sector's development paths. We draw insights from published policy documents, reports, official statements and published interviews with key stakeholders engaged in provision of TVET in both countries. We use policy narrative methods to understand and analyze policy documents and implementation responses. We then interpret legislative pronouncements that have been promulgated over time addressing changing technical and vocational education landscape in these two countries to demonstrate changes and shifts in policy implementation. In final analysis, we find significant discrepancies in policy development approaches between the two despite shared, and equally burgeoning quest for agile manpower development. China despite having to manage the largest and more complex TVET system, appear to have implemented processes that have propelled it into the largest, seemingly successful TVET system through agile policy development process. It was this very hypothesis at the onset that brought the inquest for analysis of how the two systems engage in policy development within vocational education, in spite of their size.

Keywords: TVET, Education Policy Reform, Policy Implementation, China-Africa Exchanges.

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Introduction

Study Background and Objectives

Vocational education plays a pivotal role as a dynamic and adaptable form of education, directly addressing the real-world needs of an economy. Successful vocational education systems exemplify this adaptability through continuous adjustments. Notably, literature shows China as a stand-out in vocational education, with the largest system that appears to actively equalize the social status of vocational education and general education. The works by Chen [1] and Xu [2] underscore China's progress in this domain. Despite its sheer size, China's vocational education system has emerged as one of the most pivotal models, defying initial expectations of challenges borne by size of the broader education system.

At the core of our policy analysis and research lies the fundamental requirement for vocational education to remain agile and undergo constant reform. Our study primarily focuses on technical and vocational education policy and system reforms in China and Lesotho with a summative view. While reforms are a critical aspect, we also consider the impact of the new TVET policies on the delivery of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) within Lesotho in particular, the smallest system in comparison above [3]

As stated, vocational education is driving economic productivity in developing nations especially in the east. It has formed a backbone of manpower in many that have positioned themselves as manufacturing hubs [4], [5], [6]. China has in that regard and systematically so, seemingly established the largest technical and vocational education and training –TVET system in the world[7], [8] and remains the largest manufacturing nation, essentially for the whole world. Current research also suggest it is the most successful despite the sheer size and scale. This seem to rather defy odds given the complexities of policy reform, development and implementation that is noted by local and overseas scholars in China [9].

On the other hand, Lesotho, one of the smallest nations has to a significant degree, and despite its size positioned itself as one of the most competitive manufacturing bases in Africa. This is evident in that under the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), a tariff preferential treatment by the United States to African manufacturers [10], the 2.3 million nation state had for a long time scored a top, number two spot in textile exports into the United States out of Africa. The small nation directly competed heavily with Ethiopia for the number one spot, a 132 million-nation state on a labour intensive manufacturing front, before being knocked to third place by Kenya over regulatory challenges [11], [12], [13]. It is therefore one of the most competitive nations in labour intensive manufacturing globally despite having one of the smallest populations. This does raise academic intrigue into the nature of the education system and skills development, hence this comparative review.

Therefore, in terms of TVET system and policy development, and given the high stakes involved for both the largest system – China, and one of the smallest in the world – Lesotho; both highly competitive as manufacturing bases in their own right and scale, it beckons a legitimate inquisition as to whether a smaller, relatively manageable TVET system would as well given resources, adopt, and replicate the same policy development path and implementation rigor as that of the largest system – the Chinese TVET to achieve the required manpower. A question of whether size really does matter in education systems efficiency and in this case, vocational education system. It is through this frame through which the two systems come into play, and therefore comparison, in understanding their practices of public policy development and implementation when it comes to TVET. It is assumed therefore, that due to their reliance on labour intensive manufacturing, both nations would prioritize manpower upskilling to supercharge their manufacturing capabilities despite differences in size of their education systems and by extension, vocational education system.

Given the above, the objectives of this comparative analysis are chiefly to highlight key policy differences in terms of development processes, reforms, successes and challenges and therefore opine on requisite reform, policy design, and implementation in broader African settings. This analysis is done with a view to draw lessons by providing a set of recommendations drawn specially from the two systems.

A further impetus for pursuing a comparative analysis of the two vocational education systems currently is driven by the growing attention to mutual exchanges and cooperation between the two countries in the sector, and between China and African countries in general [14]. It is worth noting a small contextual anecdote here that in terms of vocational educational exchanges, the study subject, Lesotho was mentioned in recent years within the Chinese education reports as one of the few countries in attendance at a seminar for vocational education exchanges by the Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, generally drawing assumptions that there were policy exchange learnings between the two vocational education systems.

One of these exchanges appeared in a presentation delivered by the Director General of Vocational and Adult Education Department of the Ministry of Education [1], [15]. This mention also highlights the desired cooperation between the two countries in vocational education and as highlighted in a broader context, China and Africa. Nonetheless, there is a need to make a case why this comparison is still meaningful for two vastly different education systems in terms of size, and we make such submissions in the third section of this study. In ensuing sections, however, we will take a look at the broader literature on technical and vocational education and training (TVET).

It is furthermore a given that comparing the two education policies stems from a hypothetical view to expose the underlying issues within one system. In this study Lesotho education system bears most policy implementation problems. This does not however, negate literature highlighted challenges on the former (Vocational Education in China). Below is a quick snapshot of problems that literature provides within Lesotho's vocational education system, hence a comparative review.

A summative view of the problems in vocational education development in Lesotho is principally poor outcomes borne of a weak state of education infrastructure and inadequate or stagnant policy development processes. On policy development front, before 2019 when the new Lesotho TVET policy was introduced, the previous principal law had been in place without any update for forty (40) years. The current policy document promulgated five years ago still points to the outdated principal law.

These are elementary issues that results in enrolment rates that are too low given the number of out-of-school children, unemployment rate and the quality of graduates among the small number that is enrolled annually. Moreover, the nexus between the nation's new qualification framework and the old vocational education law with previously documented capacity issues in the department presents both a new opportunity and recent problems that require a deeper review. Reviews from the official qualifications and quality assurance policy document show that it explicitly delegates the responsibility of quality assurance in vocational education and review of institutional providers squarely to the technical and vocational department of the ministry of education (TVD). It is worth noting that the Technical and Vocational Department in its own policy documents directly state that quality assurance for vocational education provision is one of the weakest points of the department.

Therefore, among key problems on Lesotho's vocational education system, the reference back to technical and vocational department for quality assurance is cardinal. It's inferred despite long-diagnosed issues of capacity within the department, poor instructor pedagogy training, and funding issues. How the national qualifications framework will maintain quality assurance given these existing challenges, and the old outdated vocational education curriculum and policy is a question that needs to be deeply probed on its own study. It is a problem of responsibility sharing and a function of actors within the network of vocational education provision in Lesotho. As just alluded to, it is a nexus point of friction that needs a comprehensive investigation along with intensive document and report reviews on the issues behind the lack of reform and development. In this instance however, we intend to reveal the intricacies of the state and

structure of these two education systems while laying groundwork and revealing patterns for probing system implan-
tation issues in both. We therefore conduct this comparative analysis, getting into the complexities of China's vocational
education development, perceiving the two systems as driven by the shared common need for rapid skills development
in labour-intensive.

But first, we end this introduction by defining and interpreting terms used in this research, and through which the study
views technical and vocational education and in the broader sense of the term – TVET.

Definition of Terms

Given the topic and keywords, we attempt to define key terms that appear in the topic, and those anticipated to
appear throughout this study being pertinent to this particular research field. The study recognises that within the
research topic, there is already an acronym, "TVET" to which the ensuing paragraphs will be dedicated to defining
more comprehensively. We therefore begin by outlining several terms that can be interpreted in varying ways to select
this study's interpretation of the related term.

There are two generic terms the study undertakes to state and define, apart from the TVET acronym. The terms are
'policy' and 'reforms. First, we define, 'system' as it refers to this field of study in education as in, "education system"
as actors, documents and processes that makeup the entire education provision. Therefore, having a bearing on the
study due to its frequent appearance as "TVET system". There are other phrases to which meaning can be inferred as a
result of defining the basic terms. These include, "policy analysis" and "policy reforms". Policy can be defined as law,
regulation, procedure, administrative action, incentive, or voluntary practice of governments and other institutions [16].
CDC also states that "policy" decisions are frequently reflected in resource allocations. In defining its scope of policy,
the CDC further adds that policy development includes the advancement and reforms of public health law. North Car-
olina State university- NCSU[17] in its definition of governing rules simply states policy as any standard, statement, or
procedure of general applicability. NCSU further helps define regulation as any standard, statement (which may in-
clude policy statement), or procedure of general applicability [17].

In scholarly descriptions, Ward, Bagley et al., (2016) quoting [18] state that, "understandings of policy have moved
beyond viewing it as a discrete entity, merely the output of a political system, to understanding policy as a process that
brings certain principles or ideas into practice [19]. The authors also indicate that the purpose of policy is for govern-
ments to 'codify and publicise the values which are to inform future practice and thus encapsulate prescriptions for
reform'. There are other various understandings of policy.

In this study, we take a combination of the two interpretations above and therefore will refer to policy as law,
regulation, procedure, administrative action, incentive and government processes intended to codify and bring certain
ideas in the public sector into practice for delivery and management of public goods and services. Therefore, given the
adopted definition, TVET policy in this study is understood and defined as comprehensive processes and actions un-
dertaken by government through laws, regulations, procedures, administrative actions, and incentives with the inten-
tion to codify, manage and bring technical and vocational education into practice within an education system of a coun-
try.

With reforms we take a more critical, but comprehensive view of the word in its standard form and contextual
meaning. We recognise the varying interpretations of 'reforms' and so the study chooses a stricter scholarly version to
ensure the interpretation covers the objectives and purpose of this study.

The term, 'system' in this study is viewed narrowly in the context of 'education system'. We do this with the un-
derstanding that the primary concern of this study is not so much on the tenets of system definition as it is for policy
and reforms, but to accept it as an augmentation to the two. Therefore, the term 'system' as it appears in the study
should be interpreted and understood as used in the field of education as in 'education system'.

A comprehensive definition of 'education system' to which this study accepts as described comes from Proctor Edu[20]. The authors describe education as the collection of institutions, policies, and practices that provide formal education to individuals within a society. It encompasses schools, colleges, universities, and other educational organizations that offer structured learning experiences to students at various stages of their educational journey [20]. Proctor Edu [20] further explains that education system involves curriculum development, teaching methods, assessment practices, and educational policies that guide the learning processes. They further write that an education system prepares students for future careers, foster critical thinking skills, promote social and cultural development, and contribute to the overall well-being and progress of society.

Notably, this view of education system also asserts that it encompasses structures, funding mechanisms, and governance bodies responsible for overseeing and managing educational institutions. INEE[21] also provides a largely similar description of education system, it asserts that an education system comprises everything that goes into educating state-school students at the state, district, or community level. It further describes it as public and private schooling from early years through to secondary school programs [21]. The definitions are therefore extrapolated and extended to cover 'TVET education system' in similar contexts of the two authors, but for vocational education, and accepted in their form. In the next paragraphs, we continue to define the term 'TVET' as it applies to the study of technical and vocational education.

Technical and vocational education and training as a term comprise various aspects of the subjects. It was first officiated as a term, technical and vocational education training at the World Congress of TVET and abbreviated as such in 1999 in Seoul Republic of Korea [22]. Various other terms have been used to describe elements of the field comprising TVET [23]. These include Apprenticeship Training, Vocational Education, Technical Education, Technical-Vocational Education (TVE), Occupational Education (OE), Vocational Educational and Training (VET), Professional and Vocational Education (PVE), Career and Technical Education (CTE), Workforce Education (WE), and Workplace Education (WE).

Malechwanz [22] further denotes concurs at the time the term TVET was recognized, it needed to be broad enough to incorporate other themes that had been loosely used to describe educational and training activities which included workforce education, technical and vocational education [24]. Technical and vocational education and training as a term comprise various aspects of the subjects.

It was first officiated as a term, technical and vocational education training at the World Congress of TVET and abbreviated as such in 1999 in Seoul Republic of Korea [22]. On the one hand technical and vocational education and training are understood as comprising education, training and skills development relating to a wide range of occupational fields, production, services, and livelihoods [24], [25]. UNESCO further defines TVET as part of lifelong learning, it defines that it can take place at secondary postsecondary and Teixeira levels and includes work-based learning and continuing training and professional development which may lead to qualifications. It also highlights that it also includes a wide range of skills development and opportunities tuned to national and local contests.

UNESCO also further denotes that TVET involves learning to learn, the development of literacy numeracy skills, transversal skills, and citizenship skills. Post-compulsory other definitions include post-compulsory education and training, excluding degrees on higher-level programs that are delivered by further education institutions which mainly provide people with occupational or work-related knowledge and skills. This also includes career and technical education which is normally used in the United States; and further education and training which is normally applied in the United Kingdom and South Africa; vocational and technical education and training which is mostly applied in Southeast Asia; vocational education and training; and vocational and technical education which is normally used as a term in Australia.

Other researchers tend to describe it in similar terms as UNESCO does. For instance, Wahba, (2013) cited in [26] also defines TVET As non-academic technical education and practical training that develops the skills and knowledge

of apprentices, which is learners of trades or crafts who are working in different sectors of industry and trainees, or students trained in different TVET institutions. The author further describes it as that part of the education system which provides courses and training programs related to employment with a view to enable the transition from secondary education to work for young trainees or students which is a social objective and apply the labour market with competent apprentice which is an economic objective.

Interestingly the author further describes TVET as a comprehensive term that refers to aspects of the educational process that involve in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of awareness, knowledge, skills, and attitudes relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life, (Wahba, 2013). TVET has also been defined as education or training process where it involves in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and acquisition of practical skills relating to occupations in various forms of economic life and social life, which comprises formal (organized programs as part of the school system) and non-formal (organized classes outside the school system) approaches, see [27], [28].

A more elaborate definition of TVET meaning is provided by [29]. It breaks the meaning based on its full term which comprises the acronym TVET. First, it describes '*Technical*' as subject matters that are technical in nature, relating to hardware and software including troubleshooting practices and engineering processes. '*Vocational*' is described as occupational employment, often referring to first-hand skills within professional trades. TVETJournal further describes '*Education*' in the term, TVET as formal education, studying in high school and including postsecondary education, such as colleges, Polytechnic, and universities. They then describe '*Training*' as informal education also called lifelong learning and continuing education often used for initiatives of re-skilling or up-skilling company staff or the wider workforce.

These definitions lead to a description and definition of TVET according to the publication as Education or training, which is technical in nature and aims to provide skills for a person related to a profession for that person to get a job and provide a livelihood [29].

Other researchers defined TVET based on either one of the Key areas of research that involves pedagogy or one of the elements in the Acronym TVET. An example of this comes from Njenga[30]. In a study of professional competencies and the continuing professional development needs of technical, vocational education and training TVET teachers in Kenya, the author describes TVET from a pedagogy standpoint in which the definition assets TVET as teacher competence, as the combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes that enable effective performance of TVET teacher roles in the content which the teacher plays the role. This view is a pedagogical definition of TVET in the context of teaching. It is however a bit far from the base definition of TVET from the rest of the authors reviewed.

Critical to this study are the definitions provided by the Lesotho Qualifications and Quality Council (LQQC), this is the new qualifications and quality assurance authority in Lesotho referred to in this study. In its glossary of terms in the newly introduced Lesotho qualifications framework [31] provides a three-tiered definition broken into technical skills, technical studies, and technical training. It defines technical skills as operational skills necessary to perform certain work and learning activities. The Council further defines technical studies as the studies of technologies-related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills in secondary schools.

It further describes technical training as training designed to prepare middle-level personnel such as technicians and middle management for employment in trade, industry and commerce and includes theoretical, scientific, and technical components and related skill training. In summary, the Council defines Technical and Vocational Education and Training as a means of education designed mainly to prepare students for direct entry into a particular occupation or trade (or class of occupations or trades). As part of the definition, the Council further complements the definition asserting that successful completion of such programs normally leads to labour market-relevant vocational qualification recognized by the competent authorities in the country in which it is obtained.

But the African Development Bank has long shunned many of these limited definitions of TVET [32] and further attributed them to the crisis that Africa went through in the 80s when the serious economic and financial crisis the

continent faced at the time generated far-reaching changes in the production system and the labour market and contributed to increasing graduate unemployment. The AfDB While adopting UNESCO and ILO TVET definitions, also decried that traditionally so-called intellectual work is often contrasted with manual work.

Thus, it says there would be, on the one hand, white-collar of these professions and, on the other, traders and technicians etc. The organization highlights that nowadays such a distinction is no longer possible even though society continues to undervalue and minimize technical education. consequently, pupils facing difficulties in their studies are those usually sent to vocational streams. Within such contexts, the organization explained that TVET systems found themselves unable to provide the skills required by the business world, facing increasing costs within the context of structural adjustment programs, and drastic budgetary reductions. Lastly, it also highlights those inadequate investments in TVET contributed to its deterioration and reduced its effectiveness.

The themes around the definition of TVET centre around the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relating to occupants in various sectors of economic and social life, skills that are meant to lead to occupations and employment equipping participants with self-help skills at both formal and non-formal, public and private institutions. Therefore, for the purposes of this study, TVET in Lesotho will be studied and referred to as such.

In defining the education system, most researchers tend to describe it either from a distinguishing perspective of formal education and informal, [33] or described from a viewpoint of private and public education. Therefore, in view of the deep intersections between public and private education, formal and non-formal education, in this study, TVET System will be defined as all processes, actors and legal apparatus designed to guide and support the reforms of TVET. While TVET Policy will then refer to basic law texts, and other government documents of record related to the regulation, provisioning, and reforms of TVET in Lesotho. Next, we take another broader view of vocational education as a research field with a focus on TVET research in Africa, and narrow down to the development pace of vocational education in both China and Africa while developing a case for comparison.

Review of Literature

Current Research on African Vocational Education

Extensive reviews on technical and vocational education reveal that it is one of the least researched areas within the education sector. Co-authored by nine other leading scholars in TVET globally, the foremost, and authoritative literature on Technical and Vocational Education in Africa comes from Simon McGrath and colleagues, prominent researchers in Vocational Education [34]. The authors in their literature review of theories that have long underpinned studies on vocational education and training for African development make some piercing criticism of the previous studies that attempted to theorize vocational education in Africa. McGrath et al., [34] argue that the majority of literature on African vocational education and training (VET) is grounded in an inadequate theorization of both VET and development and therefore they fail to fully account for political economy histories [35], [36] emerging out of colonial regimes which the authors rightly point out that such regimes are still largely responsible for what is currently present and absent in vocational education policies and debates. Therefore, the verdict is that such previous research is of limited help in driving forward discussions around strategies needed to tackle accelerating challenges faced see [37], [38], [39].

Other researchers concur with McGrath et al., [34] and go further in highlighting the actual importance of vocational education in African economies. Other notable researchers have continued to point that Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is at the forefront of research in recent years, noting that this is because it is one of the most dependable job creators for students who could neither attain nor complete university-level education [40]. As a result, most countries including Lesotho are focused on implementing and revamping their policies so that these documents help drive, and respond to challenges of employment creation and other issues surrounding the socio-economic status of people in the nation of concern [3].

But even as a subject area, current reviews and studies indicate that TVET has a set of challenges that are emanating from the very institution of this type of education. This is because in most education systems, TVET is largely instituted to accommodate students who cannot complete nor attain entrance into general higher education institutions and universities, either due to poor exit results from basic education or high school or incomplete basic education [41].

Challenges facing African TVET systems

As a result, there are some challenges surrounding the perceived value of TVET and the apparent underhandedness that surrounds its policy reforms. Researchers have noted that most policies in education that are aimed at improving TVET are failing mainly because of the uptake of students and the lack of infrastructure support for TVET institutions, see [42], [43]. There are varying arguments and contrasting motives on why TVET is not fully supported in most countries including in Africa where it is needed the most for education access and skills development.

Most of these reasons as evidenced in literatures of highlighted authors above [34], [42], [43], [44], which point amongst others to the lack of fiscal support in vocational education departments due to competing needs. Funds that are needed in supporting and achieving sufficient policy reforms. But some researchers [42], [43] note that this is mainly because of the lack of focus and lack of political will to improve TVET; its objectives, and the key role it plays in the broader education system as alluded by education departments' policy directives.

It has however become a thorn that can't be avoided, considering new students who are graduating and unable to secure employment in the job market oiling onto those who fell off in progression from basic education to higher education. It has become necessary for governments to focus on accommodating students who cannot pass through from their basic education up to higher education to complete studies in universities, equip them with requisite, and practical industry skills through vocational education channels [45]. The accommodation becomes an open opportunity for students to pursue their vocations to attain fulfilling livelihoods even though they could not complete their university education. Moreover, in some studies, see [46], [47], researchers have proven that TVET can absorb students who would otherwise become a social burden in an economy without basic production skills. In effect, because of the growing and critical role that vocational education plays, more studies have rivetted on analysing this very issue in the education domain by putting a firmer lens on TVET policy reforms [48]. This is also the focus of this study and an object of the two vocational education policies' reform and development comparison.

This research is prudent even more in Africa where studies continue to show that students who acquire skills that can be applied immediately in the industry become employable [28] and are also able to create jobs even if they did not complete and acquire university degrees and diplomas, a subject of an effective and responsive vocational education policy and implementation. The access to requisite skills training is also made possible by an increase in harmonization of vocational education qualifications in the region [49]. Nonetheless, in accordance with researchers referenced here, such students would have been heavily challenged to complete formal education through general education streams.

While vocational education in Africa remains on a catchup mode to respond to basic employability skills, it is taking a more prominent, transformed role in other developed education systems, including in China. This is a result of a well-documented and researched competition in China and a growing need for practical industry-relevant skills that the productive sectors deem highly in demand, while on the other hand, university degree curricula struggle to catch up with rapid changes in more digitized, knowledge-based, and tech-driven industries [50]. This transformation is further evidenced through increasing demand of digitized technical skills required by industries that are inherently shaped by developments in big data analysis, machine learning, mobile applications that require coding skills [51], and digital diagnostic tools in production industries including in agriculture; skills that online TVET providers are spearheading through digitization of TVET and digital skills as part of vocational training [52], [53].

Review of China-Africa Partnerships on TVET

In response to these rapidly changing landscapes in vocational education in developing and developed economies, several African governments have partnered with other experienced vocational education public providers. Specifically, African governments have partnered with the Central Government in China and other regional governments and public institutions in the country through research and development of vocational education systems, to learn from the latter’s practice and implementation [14], [54].

Fig. 1: Institutional Framework of China’s Education Assistance ([55])

The cooperation partnerships have been achieved in various forms including through the Africa-China Vocational Education Plan [56] termed “Future of Africa” which is part of the larger Forum on China Africa Cooperation. Wu[14], argues in fact that the ninth Forum on China-Africa Cooperation, “sees renewed relations and development prospects” which seemingly includes a renewed focus on vocational education as it is stated as the eighth, within the ten partnership action plans of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation, Beijing Action Plan (2025-2027) [14], [54].

The Partnership Initiatives or Action Plans as they are referred to in the Forum on China Africa Cooperation – FOCAC [55], [57] have included specific actions focused on vocational education. These include designation of 2026 as the year of people-to-people exchanges where China has vowed to continue implementing Future of Africa. Future of Africa is a project for China-Africa cooperation on vocational education, build with African countries’ schools of engineering technology, and further attested to in the same Beijing Action Plan (2025-2027) to set up or upgrade 10 Luban Workshops (TVET Workshops modeled on China’s experiences) and 20 schools. Vocational education cooperation in this regard is also more broadly guided by the South-South Cooperation framework spearheaded by China and African countries [58].

The South-South Cooperation on Development chiefly aims to observe the principle of non-interference in internal affairs, equality among developing partners and respect for their independence, national sovereignty, cultural diversity and identity and local content [55], [59]. It plays an important role in international development cooperation and is slated to be a valuable complement to the North-South cooperation.

Uneven TVET development pace, a Case for Comparison

Given the depth and context of vocational education cooperation shared above between China and African States to which Lesotho – a compared subject has been named in one of the vocational education exchanges [1], it would have been a plausible research assumption therefore that, there is to-date, stronger alignment of policy reforms and implementation techniques and processes to date – that in order to address challenges that African vocational education systems continue to face and to help fast-track sector policy development. In carrying out investigation for this comparative analysis, the study examined key knowledge and experience exchanges facilitated by the People's Republic of China in policy reform and implementation process with African states.

The reviews indicate strongly that, the pace and turnover of policy reforms in China continues to be unmatched by her peers in Africa including Lesotho [1], [60]. On the one hand, this is somewhat expected due to various comparative advantages including economics of scale, sheer experience and manpower. Conversely, a really small vocational education should be easier to manage and to make far quicker, nimble, policy reform and update to every minute industry change. But the policy reform pace and processes between China and many of her African counterparts other than Lesotho are greatly varied, and the reform, development and implementation processes may appear rather complex [9] viewed from the African policy development narratives. This is particularly the case as local researchers including Wang et al., [4] allude the same complexity in Chinese public policy processes. The broader education systems are also vastly different in terms of policy formulation approaches. That, despite numerous efforts to collaborate on the policy development front.

Outside of reports from authoritative public agencies, and dispersed remarks from key officials, current studies do not seem to fully capture the main features of policy development processes in China when it comes to vocational education. The phases to which it goes, and what informs such vocational education policy reform processes. This inhibits the ability to make a good judgement on cooperation successes in assisting African counterparts to undertake similar policy reforms in Africa. This means there are genuine questions on the extent to which local policymakers and officials in Africa have learned and understood the experiences of China, the typical route of public policy reforms and their sources, development and implementation processes, and whether these can be sufficiently localized and replicated in their context given the statecraft and public policy processes in many of the African countries.

Key to the above is not whether the cooperation is fruitful, but rather the technical policy process knowledge absorption, application acumen, and more importantly the ability to vouch for such in local contexts among lawmaking agencies, and policy stakeholders in their jurisdictions. It seems this would require an elaborate, and convincing understanding of the process acquired from the development partner, in this instance, China. As we learn next, this is more of a deeper challenge even in research.

While on the subject of learning and understanding, studying China's policy development and implementation is indeed challenging research subject to tackle, mainly due to the nature of information being difficult to obtain from direct sources, particularly public policy implementation information and research data [61], [62], [63], [64]. There are various reasons for this but for overseas researchers led projects [63], the issue of language is indeed more acute than ever emphasized. Principal documents are in local language and usually published translations and assisted peer translations do not usually contain as much of research intensive or process detailed information as would be sufficiently useful for external research purposes.

In this study however, we have attempted to capture numerous policy pronouncements, presentations and other official documents to juxtapose such in document analysis techniques to shed better light on policy reform processes, history and implementation within the vocational education sector in China and compartmentalized it for comparison and process understanding, it is an attempt. For this study as shared earlier, it is compared to that of Lesotho, in contrast, one of the smallest TVET systems in the world that would have for opposite reasons been naturally able to undertake reforms and development of a relatively easier.

The researchers have envisaged that with this comparison and results, it would contribute significant body of knowledge on why policy reforms and development fail and succeed and uncover deeper research worthy nuances negating assumptions of TVET system size as an advantage or disadvantage. In the next segments of this research, we therefore first make a case for comparison, provide the context of comparison, and the TVET policies area of comparison.

Methods and Context of Comparison

This research follows a deductive, qualitative analysis of data derived from a mixture of primary (interviews and conference proceedings) and secondary, authoritative information sources drawing insights from published policy documents, reports, official statements from key stakeholders engaged in provision of TVET in China and Lesotho (the subjects of this comparative analysis). We use policy narrative methods to understand and analyze policy documents and implementation responses. We then interpret legislative pronouncements that have been promulgated over time to address changing technical and vocational education landscape in these two countries.

Making the Case for Comparison

Lesotho and China are two infinitely different education systems in almost every narrow and broad measure possible. We outline herewith a brief on macroeconomic differences. Lesotho is a small landlocked country of about 30,355 km² with a population of just over 2.3 million. It is a least developing nation according to recent United Nations Trade and Development – UNCTAD classification [65], though classified as a lower middle-income country by the World Bank [66]. It is located in southern Africa. The average person earns about \$589 in some estimates, while the GDP per capita is about \$1061 last measured in 2023, according to the World Bank [66]. Lesotho operates one of the smallest education systems in the world that is developing and under a relatively slow reform process driven mainly by the nation's development partners.

China on the other hand is the second largest economy in the world where the average salary per person is around \$1392, more than double that of Lesotho, and a GDP per capita of about \$12,969, which is over ten times that of Lesotho. China has the largest population in the world of any nation and by extension operates the largest education system in all subsectors of education. China's education system is constantly developing and gradually reaching an advanced, well-developed stage [7].

At phase value, there is a strong inclination to suggest there is no case for comparison between the two countries, and even more so to come up with meaningful conclusions due to sheer differences in size. These differences could therefore be interpreted to mean that making a comparison between these two nations would be fruitless and could lead to misplaced recommendations emanating from the complexities of their difference in education systems. Even on the normative comparisons of large versus small dynamics, it could be argued that the differences here are significant to a point that it would be better to take a subset of the larger instead. That is, to take a city within China with relative comparison to Lesotho and make the case for comparison. While the latter sounds plausible, it could however lead to even more confusion and misaligned recommendations in context due to different application of policy development processes at local versus national level. It would deprive the reader of the context of application to understand the underlying policy directives. Furthermore, and mostly critical in policy analysis, the approach could wrongly highlight localized policy adaptations as a reflection of national policy direction and focus. The approach may further inherit performance and outcomes of local reforms as those at national level results in the context of applying remedies for the latter (reforms at national level in Lesotho).

The context of comparison

From the above, it is important that context should be taken into account to make meaningful comparisons. Context matters in policy reviews and comparisons because it can provide an opportunity for comparison even between subjects

that are vastly different in nature and structure. This is also a reference to issues of policy development process and statecraft at national level. Regardless of the size, the process of policy formulation, change and implementation at national or local level follows a relatively common process derived from common literatures of policy change and implementation in terms of stakeholder engagement [67], [68], which would then allow for a comparison of process and execution in two different governments and countries. It is in the very context that common evaluation models are drawn between subjects in order to assess and compare different regions with differing economic status especially in education. A special reference here is made to the Systems Approach for Better Education Results (SABER) used by the World Bank to collect, analyse, and disseminate comprehensive information on education policies around the world [69]. While SABER is not the model used for comparison in this study, and is mainly used to compare the results of policy implementation across similar metrics, it is of important reference to drive a point that the three are systems such as these that exists to establish that comparison can be made on similar policy initiatives across different contexts especially in education policy.

Given the subject of public policy comparison, it is possible to compare Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) policies between any two given countries at national level. This makes it possible to undertake comparative studies of TVET policies between Lesotho and China. As it is highlighted earlier, the context and contents of comparison are key here. That is, the contents of policy comparisons should contain elements that are comparable in nature. Therefore, this particular comparison will entail several areas of TVET policies in the two countries that are deemed comparable due to their generality in assessment regardless of size, with emphasis on the documents reveal a model that was implemented by [70] as they studied policy reforms processes in Chile. The model suggests that policy reform comes in stages through which certain activities and pronouncements can be drawn to inform patterns. This is encapsulated in Cultural Political Economy (CPE) processes. The tenets of the CPE theory suggest that policy reform process goes through four main stages, Policy Variation, Selection, Retention, and Reform Activity. While we are not able to directly compare these processes independently for these countries, we are still able to see certain areas of policy reform processes that are evident through the CPE lens for comparison.

Fig. 2: Cultural Political Economy Policy Reform Process (Zancajo & Valiente, 2019)

Areas of TVET policies comparison

The study will first take a brief look at the structure of vocational education from law texts in both countries. We then provide a snapshot of the state of TVET in both countries by providing key statistical data to quantify the size of vocational education in both countries, invertedly highlighting the differences in sizes. Secondly, we look at the sources of policy documents for both countries to understand the process of formulating TVET policies and the nature of adoption. Third, we look at the contents and scope of TVET policies in both countries to understand at a higher-level, the focus of the policymakers in formulating either vocational education polices or how vocational education is captured in policy documents related to the subsector and in general, the broader education system in both countries. Forth, we look at policy development history. The aim here is to understand the tenets and sources of vocational or technical

education approaches, and its development phases over a longer period of time. Where possible, we aim to provide a better understanding of how vocational education evolved in the two countries to inform current state of TVET in each country.

Next, and at the crux of this comparative study, we highlight then and make brief analysis of key differences in TVET policies looking at four key areas. We look at the key differences in the process of development, reforms, successes and challenges. The differences highlighted here certainly do not encompass all the areas of a typical public policy analysis areas. They are especially selected for analysis in this comparison in realization of the differences in the sizes of the study subjects. This means that the aspects of policy areas selected for analysis like development, reforms, implied and or perceived policy successes and challenges can easily be compared regardless of the size of the subjects. This is in relative practical reality that development can be slow or fast; frequent or seldom regardless of size. Furthermore, policy reforms can be successful or remain challenged regardless of the size of the education system. The latter may simply aid in adding a level of difficulty or ease in each process.

There is therefore a realization that the normal economic limitations and advantages brought by the economics of scale may also be at play in the observed analysis results. But the means are also relative and therefore necessitates comparison. In the sixth and final section in the comparison are recommendations. Here the focus will be made more on Lesotho. There is a case to be made that there is more to learn for Lesotho's education system on China than there is for China in Lesotho's education system, this notwithstanding eventual mutual learning in exchanges between the two systems.

State and Structure of TVET in China and Lesotho

In this section, and unlike the rest of the sections that will follow, we take a deep-dive analysis on the structure and state of TVET systems in both Lesotho and China starting with Lesotho. The whole-whole approach here is necessitated by the sheer differences in structure and state that it only makes analytical difference when each is taken in a subsection for all that can be analysed in each of the system. In the other sections, starting with the section on Sources of Policy Documents etc., the study makes immediate comparisons in a piece-meal approach in anticipation that the differences will be immediately clear.

The state and structure of TVET in Lesotho

The legal framework and development of vocational education in Lesotho had an earlier start to that of China [71]. But that is just about one of the only two key items observed in the rest of the documents of record where Lesotho seemed to have had an advanced standing. Literature suggests that it is relatively downhill from there onwards in terms of progress and development. Lesotho introduced the first legal document recognizing technical and vocational education into law in 1984, which came into operation in 1987 [72]. Vocational education in Lesotho is part of the entire public education in Lesotho which starts at primary education to tertiary or higher education [3].

Learners follow a converged path where they can interchange between general education, referred to as academic or take the technical education route. Technical and vocational education in Lesotho is nested within the education sector plan which runs for periods of 10 years. The current education sector plan began in 2016 and will end in 2026 [73].

The governance of technical and vocational education in Lesotho is undertaken by the Technical and Vocational Department of the Ministry of Education of Lesotho. The department however does not completely regulate provision of technical education within basic education, that is, it does not own or operate entire secondary or primary education institutions in the country and private TVET providers remain largely unregulated especially smaller vocational centres spread across the country [3].

A separate department is dedicated to governance of all teaching, resourcing and curriculum development in basic education. The department does however oversee curriculum in about 93 secondary schools that offer technical and vocational education. Subjects including technology and innovation which mainly refer to the original woodwork and metal works, technical drawing and design, and home economics and agriculture are the main subjects that TVD oversees in secondary education.

There is a broader spectrum of TVET programs at higher vocational education with Carpentry and Joinery, Bricklaying and Plastering, and Sewing and Tailoring being the top 3 at 19%, 15% and 19% of overall vocational education programs offered in formal TVET institutions respectively.

Fig. 3: Most popular TVET Programs in Lesotho (MoET, 2016)

This leaves TVD with overseeing full provision and entire institution governance of TVET in higher education mostly in public providers and in some private provision with both formal and non-formal providers. TVD is in charge of about 20 technical and vocational institutions across the country which provide varying levels of vocational education with even vastly differing quality of programs across the entire spectrum of public and private provision [3].

The department also oversees about 19 industries in which companies provide experimental opportunities for traineeship schemes and internship opportunities for learners. All these happen at postsecondary level. The government owns about 8% of the registered institutions that provide vocational education in Lesotho. There are about 2% which are owned by churches or religious institutions which also dominate the basic education provision. Some 24% of the institutions are community owned. Interestingly and in contrast to China, about 46%, almost half of known or registered vocational education providers in Lesotho are privately owned. This means that apart from government and church institutions, about 70% of all vocational education institutions in Lesotho are operated by either the community or privately run. TVET sector in Lesotho has been noted in the past for demand that exceeds supply due to extremely low enrolment rates across different vocational education institutions in the country [31]. The sector suffers from high dropout rates, and a lack of baseline studies means there is little evidence of the employment rates of the sector. There are inferences to poor employment rates emanating from old curriculum that has long been surpassed by current industrial demands in the labour market in majority of institutions, particularly government run institutions which also provide the largest number of regulated and recognized diplomas.

There are about 6000 technical education learners in junior secondary schools in Lesotho. There is a relatively equal number in senior secondary and rather low figure of around 3000 students in higher vocational education institutions.

TVD has made bold plans to enrol a total of about 18000 learners at junior school and about 10000 for senior secondary and a seemingly lower enrolment of about 3500 at higher vocational education institutions by 2026. The sector plans to reform vocational education by the end of the current education sectoral plan 2016 - 2026 by further ensuring that 100% of learners and 40% of instructors and technical teachers complete long term and short-term training. These efforts would be complemented by ensuring at least a 30% industry-based training for technical and vocational education learners with cooperation of the industry [3], [73]. This is brief snapshot of the state of vocational education in Lesotho from basic, secondary to higher vocational education.

The state and structure of TVET in China

The structure and state of vocational education in China is characterized and continually shaped by constant adjustments in policy and practice to respond to the needs of the labour market, and changing technological advancements [74], [75], [76], [77]. China implements vocational education with an avid focus on higher technical education. Basic education system with Chinese characteristics as referred to is also shaped by the ongoing empirical model of reform and development in the rest of the sectors in the country. Vocational education in China is governed under the Ministry of Education of China through the Vocational and Adult Education Department. This is the department entrusted with policy formulation and reforms of vocational and technical education in China [1].

May, 1996 was the first time that higher vocational education was guaranteed by law in China through the enactment of the Vocational Education Law of the People's Republic of China [1]. While this was a little over ten years since Lesotho had passed a similar vocational education law, this would be the only difference in terms of a head start as stated earlier. At the onset, the Chinese TVET law text stipulated that, "vocational education is divided into primary, secondary and higher vocational education." [1]. The law further stated that, "Higher vocational school and education shall be carried out by higher vocational colleges, or if necessary, by ordinary institutions of higher learning."

Further down, two years later since the first statute purposely crafted to formalize and regulate TVET in China, the country passed, "The Law of the People's Republic of China on Higher Education in August, 1998. While this law affected the broader provision of higher education in China, the statute was still quite significant in further establishing the legal status of higher vocational education in the country. This is because in description of "higher education institutions", the law referred them to as "universities, independently established colleges and other colleges including higher vocational education schools and adult institutions of higher learning" [1], [60].

In further strengthening the existence and reforms of vocational education in China, the Ministry of Education formulated and put forward an, "Action Plan for the Revitalization of Education for the 21st Century [1], [15]. In this action plan, the Ministry of Education of China stressed that, "Higher education must be oriented towards regional economic construction and social development, adapt to the actual needs of the job market, and train practical talents in production, service, and management of the first line of needs." [1]. It is imperative to note the ending tone of the action plan in the quoted statement. The adherence to "actual needs of the job market", "practical talents", "first line of needs" would in summative view serve as a hallmark of the ensuing constant adjustments alluded to in earlier statements. Perhaps a cornerstone that separates vocational education in China to most other countries including in Lesotho, is the ability and willingness to constantly adjust policy without fear of "Path Dependence Theory" costs as alluded to by Cerna [68] to meet key demands set out by policy documents in their response to the labour market conditions. There exists a thriving debate and whole body of literature examining the reluctance of policy change due to this very theoretical view of path dependence [67], [68] which basically suggests that policymakers would rather stick to known systems and policies than to change or reform existing ones in fear of the costs of replacement policy. It is however an apparent ominous stance with regard to an education type that basically becomes obsolete if drastic changes are not taken to update this type of education (vocational education) system in light of industry and labour-market changes.

In summary of vocational education changes, China went through four main stages of policy reforms process [1], [60] characterized in the following manner as:

- **Starting Stage** – 1949-1977,
- **Exploring Stage** – 1978 - 1998,
- **Vigorous Development** – 1999-2013,
- **Featured Development** – 2014 -2024.

During these four stages of development, which can't be immediately classified in terms of Lesotho's vocational education development, workforce development in China went through series of heavy investments. For China's economic strategies, these investments notably coincided squarely with other significant activities in the economy, including bids to join the World Trade Organisation [78], [79] and its predecessor organisation, General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade – GATT [80].

Fig. 4: Vocational Education Development Cycle in China, (Chen [1] Xu [2]).

In a period spanning over 70 years, China has made historic leaps in vocational education, and has seen breakthroughs in the period. It is indeed the largest vocational education system in the world. There are a little over 12000 vocational education institutions in China recorded that offer a combined 120000 specialties [74]. There were over 30 million current students and an enrolment rate of over 10 million students in Chinese vocational education institutions. Notably, the employment rate of vocational education institutions graduates across China stood at 90% for several years over the development of the education subsector until 2024 [15], [74]. It is evident from the above statistics that China would have effectively built the world's largest vocational education system.

Vocational education in China covers all sectors of TVET provision in terms of administration through the Department of Vocational and Adult Education [1], [81]. It covers enrolment, teaching and curriculum, student support, management and further aspects of regulatory and administration that our literature review shows may be overlooked in other TVET systems in the world. These include aspects of investment, system standards and priority distinguished by national, provincial, municipal and county level; and direct industry and enterprise participation in the provision of vocational education. To fully administer vocational education in China, the country set up over 50 industry vocational education steering committees which collectively brought together over 3000 experts from all kinds of trades,

specifically to guide the organisation of vocational education [1], [7], [77], [81]. The Department of Vocational and Adult Education further issued a directory of about 770 professional specialties. It further provided about 410 higher vocational professional teaching standards, 230 vocational professional teaching standards, 136 vocational schools professional (class) top-post internship standards, and 30 vocational colleges professional practical training conditions construction standards, that is professional equipment specifications) including identification and establishment of model vocational education centres for mutual learning across provinces and municipalities. The department further adjusted the qualifications system in higher education, and in 2019 piloted the 1+X certification system whose purpose is to mainly improve the employability of people who have received vocational education in the country [74]. This system has reached over 1000 vocational colleges and universities with a total student reach of over 240000.

Vocational education in China is further driven by a deliberate focus on equity and inclusion by implementing policy initiatives aimed at ensuring that this kind of education is reachable to all families and remains of higher quality [7], [60], [82]. To that end, the department continually raises the standard of allocation for secondary and higher vocational students and implements improvement plans, and in particular, the integration of production and education and pioneered key vocational colleges, specialties and teachers. The concept of model TVET institutions in this form is further viewed as a key pillar of modernization and standardization of vocational education across the country.

In a bid to further enhance inclusion, the department runs a large financial aid system to help students from disadvantaged backgrounds access vocational education for tuition free bursaries and grants that cover 90% and 40% of learners respectively at secondary vocational schools and about 30% and 25% for those who are enrolled in higher vocational education colleges see Chen, MOE, Postiglione and Tang [1][74][82]. These programs are augmented by an experience sharing mechanism that recognizes inadvertently that development over vast regions will not be at the same par. To that end, and in a further bid to aid equity, the department implements the East-West Cooperation Action Plan for vocational education to provide vocational education to farmers and guide the rural transfer of labour, for the laid off or unemployed and the disabled. This specific policy has specially made significant contribution to lifting over 10 million people out of poverty in recent years [1].

The other key component that continues to shape vocational education in China revolves around industrial connectivity. To pursue further industrial connectivity, vocational education in China promotes employability and showcasing of skills at national contests such as the China Skills national contest and other activities at secondary education level [74]. All these initiatives are clued together by compiling an annual report on one; the quality of higher vocational posts, and the national secondary vocational school employment analysis [1], [60], [74]. These would appear key sector documents particularly the latter, since it attempts to gauge the attractiveness of vocational education over the years of reports. The above entails the key tents, structure, and state of vocational education in China. It is evidently more detailed and has more research conducted on the sector.

Sources of policy documents for Lesotho and China

Lesotho vocational education policy was passed in 2019 as Lesotho Technical and Vocational Education Act 2019 [3]. It is used and based on the developments made from the initial law governing reforms of TVET in the country. It is developed from the Technical and Vocational Training Act of 1984 [72]. This was the principal law that guaranteed vocational education in the country and made it a formal means of attaining skills through organized training. Despite the late introduction of the act, which still took a further 3 years for it to be implemented [71]. There were several vocational education institutions which were prominently providing vocational education in the country. There are other several policy documents which make reference to the development of vocational education in Lesotho. These documents include the main education law which was amended several times until 2021 [83].

Further policy pronouncements can be found in three other policy documents in Lesotho. These documents encompass the entire education system. TVET is further mentioned in the Lesotho Qualifications Framework (LQF) which is administered and implemented by the Lesotho Qualifications Council [31], a body that is entrusted with quality assurance and standardization of qualifications. Importantly, the LQF further streamlines general education and vocational education by introducing a harmonised credit system, and a credit transfer system on which students on either side of the education sector (general/ vocational) can transfer credits to the other to pursue their desired paths: The Credit Accumulation and Transfer – CAT, “Recognition of Prior Learning – RPL and Recognition of Current Competences – RCC applies equally in all sectors across all qualifications, whether in general, TVET, (academic or professional) awards”[31]. In order to facilitate a streamlined and coherent system, the LQF contains the following generic qualification types as indicated above: Degrees, Diplomas, Certificates, professional development awards, vocational qualifications, and modern apprenticeships. The principles and nomenclature used in naming qualifications is important according to the qualifications’ agency, in order to reflect the purposes and outcomes of the diverse scope across General/Academic / Professional and TVET tracks within the LQF [31]. The approach used also provides the structure to streamline qualifications and as introduced earlier, enable credit accumulation and transfer (CAT), recognition of prior learning, (RPL) and recognition of current competences, (RCC). This shows that the Lesotho Qualifications Framework is by extension a key policy document that solidifies provision and recognition of vocational education qualifications in the country. These documents proposed and enacted largely by policy entrepreneurs from the government agencies with some contribution of other stakeholders acting within the agency’s network of established committees are act as sources of policy for vocational education.

On the other hand, China’s vocational education policy sources appear quite dispersed through established steering committees, though final policy documents are a centralized action of the central government through the government agency responsible (Department of Vocational and Adult Education). Policy pronouncements have been made several years before the actual passage of the basic law guaranteeing vocational education in China [1]. In the 70 years since the founding of the People’s Republic of China, direct reference to vocational education was prominently made on May 27, 1985 through a Central Committee decision on the “Reform of the Education System” which stated in part, “To actively develop higher vocational and technical colleges and universities, and gradually establish a vocational and technical education system from primary to advanced level, industry support, with reasonable structure and can communicate each other with the general education” [1], [81].

There is significant evidence with the case of China that vocational education has a direct impact on industrial development, and therefore economic development strategy. China went through various stages of education reforms, particularly TVET that correlated with significant changes in the economic development strategies.

Fig. 5: Authors' Illustration of Policy Reform Cycle in China

There were several other official pronouncements that serve as key sources of vocational education policy made over the years since 1985 including in 1991 through a decision of the State Council of China on the "Great Development of Vocational and Technical Education" [1], [31]. The decision chiefly clarified the positioning and role of vocational education. There were two more policy pronouncements in June and July of 1994 by the National Work Conference of China and the State Council of China respectively. The latter put forward "Reforms Opinions on China's Education Reform and Development Program," thereby stating that through the reform of existing colleges, vocational universities and adult colleges and universities, as well as the holding of flexible and diverse higher vocational classes, the state would develop higher vocational education.

It was however on the 15th of May 1996 that The Vocational Education Law of the People's Republic of China was promulgated [1], [74], [81], and as stated earlier, the first time higher vocational education in particular was guaranteed by law. To provide more context, the statute stated among others that, "higher vocational school education shall be carried out by higher vocational colleges, or if necessary, by ordinary institutions of higher learning [81]. Article 13 of the law further stated that, "Vocational school education includes primary, secondary and higher vocational school education." Other Articles of the statute further stated that primary and secondary vocational school education shall be carried out respectively by primary and secondary vocational education.

On December 24th 1998, the Ministry of Education of China put forward the "Action Plan for the revitalization of Education for the 21st century" [1], [81]. It was in this action plan, that the Ministry of Education plainly stated what was alluded to earlier in the section discussing the *State and Structure of Vocational Education in China* in our study; the plan stated, "Higher vocational education must be oriented towards regional economic construction and social development, adapt to the actual needs of the job market, and train practical talents in production, service and management of the first line of needs." This was a major policy indication that there would be more emphasis on higher vocational education so that it can be steered towards responding to the actual economic needs of the country at national and differentiated at local level based on regional needs. This was a sharp emphasis of single but customizable approach to TVET policy implementation within a country. Therefore, this document is one of the key sources of vocational education policy in China.

In a testament to the agile and nimble nature of policy changes in China, there were further significant strides toward reform of vocational education sector. It was further adjusted constantly to respond to the actual needs of the economy and the labour market in China and varying regions. These included Ministry of Education's "Reforms Opinion" on the "Piloting Organisation of Higer Vocational and Technical Education in 1999", the "Opinions on Strengthening the Training of Personnel in Higher Vocational Education" putting forward the expression of "double teacher" in 2000", and further down to 2006 with the Ministry's "Opinions on speeding up the reform and Development of Higher Vocational Education", "focusing on supporting the construction of 100 national model higher vocational colleges." [1], [15], [60], [74].

These efforts culminated with six departments including the Ministry of Education of China issuing the "Plan for the construction of modern vocational education system (2014-2020)" and stated the following as the main objective of the plan, "Accelerate the pace of reform of the higher vocational schools". These policy proposals culminated with the newest source of policy document for vocational education in China. This is the "Revised Vocational Education Law of the of the People's Republic of China" [60], [74], [76], [77], [84]. This law was initially adopted at the 19th Meeting of the Standing Committee of the Eighth National People's Congress on May 15, 1996, and revised at the 34th Meeting of

the Standing Committee of the Thirteenth National People's Congress on April 20, 2022. The document in reference provides a cardinal snapshot of key vocational education policies in China's TVET system.

There is great variance between Lesotho and China when it comes to the initial introduction of a policy, and variation sources especially when viewed through the lens of the earlier introduced theoretical framework of Cultural Political Economy. Both processes can however be explained more broadly through the Advocacy Coalition Framework – ACF [68], [85], [86], [87], where there are system subsets of actors working to drive certain ideas of policy developments through a prism of shared social beliefs that can be explained through examination of content of the policy documents [67], [68]. Within Lesotho however, these sources of actual policy come from a myriad of actors largely concentrated within the internal government agency (department policymakers and those in recognized committees cited by the statute), with some level of consultation outside, to other actors of the coalition subnet as illustrated by Cerna, (2013). Furthermore, with regard to Lesotho policy processes, there is evidence from practice observation of unstructured political initiatives to reform public policy following change theories of *punctuated equilibrium* [68], [88], [89], arising out of external events that disrupt the political system (statistics of high unemployment etc.). These are may however be knee-capped by the closed nature of policymaking process under the change framework of ACF as explained above. The punctuated equilibrium frames of policymaking has had some success however, with the introduction of free primary education in the early 2000s, whereas Cerna, (2013) and Baumgatner and Jones (1991) had framed, the political actors, capable of strategic action, employed a dual strategy: they seemed to change participants in policy advocacy and therefore had managed to control the image of the policy problem through the use of rhetoric, symbols and policy analysis. Those actions filtered into the inner agency actors and resulted in policy implementation. This was the strongest indication of political support to policy reform that was met with actual policy action on government by the actors while in government. This is arguably and with less literature evidence suggesting otherwise, a rarer source of policy introduction and variation in Lesotho. Moreover, macroeconomic dynamics of Lesotho indicate that much of the development budget is financed by multilateral development organisations [90].

The development organisations in Lesotho are the main policy drivers through funding into research and surveys that end up informing and compelling policy reform in the public sector. It is from the results of such survey's that policy proposals are forwarded to government departments for further formulation [90], [91]. The whole process can be donor-agency funded until a particular policy document is produced and tabled before cabinet.

This process is quite different with China. In China documents of record indicate that much of the policy proposals actually come from the frontlines upwards through working and research groups [1], [60]. It is evident with the development path of vocational education in China that several steering committees at local governments and upwards were responsible and acted on policy initiatives for introduction and variation [74]. For instance, with regard to the overall management of vocational education, the whole country set up 56 industry vocational education steering committees. These as stated earlier brought together 3000 experts from different sectors of the economy, and were charged with setting up the industry and to guide vocational education organisation platform. The Ministry of Education of China further publishes sectoral reports [74], including one for vocational education. The existence and review of this report indicates that research plays a pivotal and active role to produce a complete image of the state of vocational education in the country through the annual report; making universities and research institutions key sources of policy introduction and variation through awarded projects to inform the reform and development of related public policy.

Analysis of key policy differences

There is already ample literature evidence revealed in previous sections on the differences of the two vocational education policies. From the manner in which policy formulation and change is approached; to the level of adjustments and comprehensiveness of each of these approaches; and most notably, the comparable results as annotated in each of the country's policy and document reviews. In this section we will attempt to briefly summarize key obvious policy

differences. We will cover four areas that in analysis indicate significant differences in terms of approach and execution. We will therefore briefly highlight, process of policy development, reforms, successes, and challenges.

In terms of the process of policy development, China utilizes a systematic method of research and continuous data collection as encouraged in the law governing vocational education in the country. This does not appear to be the case in review of Lesotho's policy development process, there are no references to research and data collection from practice in any documents related to vocational education including in the principal TVET policy document. The lack of reports seems to be the main indicator of such regarding the state of TVET in the country. Moreover, vocational education in China undergoes constant adjustment and action plans. In review of literature forwarded by Chen (2019) and MOE (2022), there is evidence that every two years there is a major policy adjustment in China that seeks to adjust and improve the state of vocational education in the country – while every year, the Ministry of Education of China makes a pronouncement on some areas of vocational education provision. There are years when a major reform action is undertaken at State Council. This approach is the most evident difference to the process of policy development in Lesotho.

With regard to policy change and reforms, China takes a real-time, market condition-based approach to implement, and change policy. This is stated in policy documents as a measure to ensure that curriculum and programs provided at regional level actually respond to the localities needs in the labour market. That is, the actual needs of specific industries and localities at even county level. In previous sections, we introduced the concept of reforms as a research effort to make governance analysis and operations in executing policy proposals. In this regard, policymakers in China seem to have made efforts to implement vocational education policy by making policy priorities clear and outlining areas of focus across different regions. This approach may have uncovered a need to ensure that higher vocational education is given prominence to aid in regional economic development. The approach may have also resulted in the observed, targeted efforts to improve the teaching material and teacher training, and deliberate efforts push reforms, promote educational equity with rationed scholarships and annual increases in school allocations for vocational students. There are evident deliberate efforts in policy statements to promote connectivity through industry events that give learners opportunities to grow, and build an international outlook to share experiences. All these indicate a comprehensive reform that mirrors initial policy proposals. It is hard to make an objective view of how this matches up with policy reforms in Lesotho given the number of times that the government has made public pronouncements of similar nature without implementation of such which were also intended to improve the reforms efforts. Therefore, in terms of reforms, China has made notable and deliberate efforts to execute the provisions of the national policy on vocational education, while in Lesotho this effort appears fragmented and stagnant.

On policy successes, China has seemingly built the largest vocational education system that is highly responsive to real time market changes in terms of curriculum and program design. While Lesotho cannot build the largest vocational education system, a comparable measure here is coverage as a ratio of need. By the end of 2021 in a major milestone report of vocational education reforms in China between 2012 and 2021 in the era of "Featured Development" [1], [75]), China bolstered vocational education with sizable figures that are comparable. Vocational education centres that were co-established with enterprises grew by 8.6 percent annually. China modified programs over the same period, and removed 108 outdated disciplines; upgraded or added about 1007, this represented a modification rate of over 70%. The country now offers over 1300 disciplines and 12000 programs noting that over 70% of new frontline workers are graduates of vocational schools [74], [76], [84]. In 2021 a total of 1891 higher education institutions in China offered degree programs through continuing education with registered students accounting for about 46.8% of the total number of undergraduates.

Capturing all these in a snapshot, in 2019, the Ministry estimated that China had about 27 million students in enrolment, but two years later in 2021 report, the number had risen to 30 million representing an increment of over 10% in enrolment on a year-on-year basis. This is a growth enrolment rate in vocational education that neither Lesotho nor many African TVET system realize in five to years period. There is no report on current data regarding these in Lesotho

on similar metrics that are equally comparable apart from the national projections shared earlier – those were not rather optimistic projections nonetheless. Furthermore, and with regard to Lesotho, there has been efforts to review programs, revamp curriculum, and to build and repair vocational education schools. There hasn't been much data to this effect still, but indications in terms of student growth do not suggest a great outlook. For instance, UNESCO-UNEVOC (2022) data showed that in the years leading to 2012, 2013 and 2014, gross enrolment rate was at 3296 for Junior Secondary, 3303 for Senior Secondary and 4223 for higher vocational education institutions. By 2020 these numbers were estimated to stand at 5995, 5957, and 2986. It should be noted that the education sector plan has intentions to increase the number of junior secondary school students taking vocational education to 17, 871, 9429 for senior secondary and 3423 for higher vocational education students. While there is a shift to increase the number of students taking vocational education subjects in junior secondary and a relatively moderate effort to increase teacher recruitment and resources, this figure represents a growth of about 14% over a five-year period. But in absolute figures, a 3423-enrolment at higher vocational education institutions appears harmless due to an expected size of the education system in Lesotho. That is until it is revealed that actually over 17000 students' seat for exams to enter higher education with an enrolment rate less than 60%. This means that at 3423 rates of enrolment (increasing over time), at least about 50% of those who seat for Lesotho's high school leaving examinations do not have a path for either general education, or even formal vocational education, and this is a repeated cycle year-over-year.

When it comes to the two countries challenges to vocational education policies, the challenges of TVET provision in China are quite complex and advanced in nature. These are driven largely by the need to achieve advanced level, issues surrounding quality of higher vocational education programs in some areas, and a need for further development of the curriculum. However, one of the emerging themes and a result of the two systems of education in merged as one is the harmonisation of TVET with general education in China. That is, a direct admission, assessment and equivalence of degrees and credits between students who went through general education, and sat for the country's notably difficult and extremely competitive high school leaving examination known in communities of education policy practice in China as "Gaokao" – and students who went through vocational education and most likely unsuccessfully sat or did not even seat for the same college entrance examination. There are plausible expectations that a qualifications framework that directly weighs credits between general education and vocational education with links to equated admissions or things like recognition of prior learning – RPL as is the case in Lesotho, or recognition of current competences – RCC against those of general education would go a long way to prove statements that general education is equal, and the same as vocational education [2], [60], [76]. These efforts could greatly improve enrolment, social status, and acceptance of vocational education as a main stream option for different talents.

The challenges with Lesotho's vocational education are elementary and have been laid out in the main body of this study. These are really nascent reform challenges of basic access. The vocational education system is archaic, and in desperate need of reform. The challenges of the policy emanate from research. Lesotho education system needs to collect evidence of the real status of vocational education comprehensively beyond policy analysis and make such available to advocacy networks including researchers for dissection of propositions. These would need to happen through practical sector surveys, and then produce a reflective factual report based on such. The cardinal act required from Lesotho's education system actors is to repeal and replace the Technical and vocational Training Act of 1984, it is evident that the old principal law act as the main impediment to reform and development of the sector.

Vocational education law in Lesotho currently does not explicitly guarantee access to vocational education through enrolment minimums in both secondary and tertiary institutions. A model that can be based on factors such as dropout rates and graduation rates to ensure that there is equitable access to vocational education. While the country developed a policy document recently in 2019, the policy document is heavily limited by its reference to the old principal law. That is even more challenging since even with the introduction of a new principal law, the current policy document on its own is heavily deficient in aiding implementation directives and as stated guaranteeing important elements like quotas,

requirement of research and production of reports, development and review of curriculum and circumstances under which those should take place. The policy document does not include concrete reform and development targets that are really achievable and/ or measurable. As highlighted, the policy does not principally require, but simply encourages research, critical in particular to this type of labour-market sensitive education. This is a key factor in determining real market needs and technology changes. This then results in archaic programs of which the government continues to fund, especially in public TVET institutions, even though they have been documented to be obsolete by graduates over the years in reference to the needs in the labour market.

With a lack of focus on reform and development, the policy lacks action plans that aid changes to the vocational education system in the country. Therefore, the policy lives on assumptions of economic needs, not directly related to real-time productive sectors. This evidently suggests that in Lesotho, the actual practice of TVET is driven by a policy document that it is supply driven, and not demand driven. In promising statement of policy, the document aspires for a national coordinating body to undertake vocational education training, which can only be achieved by promulgation of a new law. The current law does not support creation of the said body. This represents a significant challenge to successful reforms of vocational education system in the country. Lastly, the policy still envisages the aspired national coordinating bodies to self-regulate quality assurance and qualifications. This is another key challenge since there is already an established national qualifications body in Lesotho to which any other similar body should be structured within, and effectively repeal any provisions within the LQF that suggest otherwise, (which the LQF policy actually does in referring to vocational education quality assurance). There is a large body of literature that suggests this would be the beginning of a rather chaotic administration of qualifications and assessment of quality especially in a harmonized environment. The existence of the harmonized qualifications body in Lesotho is in fact, one area where the country is advanced in terms of management of general education and vocational education. These are relatively a sum of challenges facing Lesotho compared to those of China's vocational education system.

Recommendations

Policy Reforms

There are several recommendations that can be drawn from the analysis of both China and Lesotho's vocational education systems in previous sections. First, it is clear that Lesotho needs to view vocational education as an agile education system even more than it does general education. As noted in earlier reports, China was clear of the fact that vocational education is sensitive to changes in the market needs and shifts in technological advancements. Therefore, this necessitated constant changes that culminated in a modern vocational education policy and law that responds to current demands.

Essentially, the recommendations for Lesotho are ideally encapsulated in another measure employed by China to improve vocational education. This is in undertaking of data collection, studies and research then producing timely reports of the state of vocational education to inform policy development and reform of the sector. In its review of the achievements in vocational education between 2012 -2021, China has celebrated successes that are in turn strong lessons for Lesotho's future development of vocational education. There first milestone was alignment with economic and social development. The law further promoted education-production integration. It established a direct link with academic education, strengthened the vertical link between vocational education at different levels of administration, from national down to county level.

In a lesson for Lesotho, vocational education policy in China has improved the capacity of its education and training. Something that has been extremely slow in terms of development in Lesotho. The policymakers in China actively seek integration with the broader multilateral communities, including support to the country's trade initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative. It proposes mutual exchanges and the creation of avenues for technical expertise and training through projects like Lu Ban Workshops where policymakers share experiences and expertise by training technicians

in other countries. The Lu Ban Workshop is the one project which Lesotho may want to participate in, and to further develop its capacity so that vocational education can serve the critical purpose it is intended.

There are indeed several more lessons which can be drawn from a TVET system like that of China. Vocational education system in Lesotho is governed by the 1984 Act of Technical and Vocational Training (African Union Development Agency, 2023). The National Strategic Development Plan 2012/13-2016/17 focuses on skills development for economic growth (African Union Development Agency, 2023). The plan suggests that for Lesotho to exploit the 'demographic bonus' of its large young labour force, the Ministry of Education and Training (MoET) should raise skills development by specifically focusing on improving relevance and applicability of skills, expansion and upgrading of TVET institutions to support growth sectors (African Union Development Agency, 2023). This vision requires a far more research and data informed policy development process, something this comparison has revealed has been the source for Chinese system.

China has a "modern" TVET system that is led by government agencies, but works closely with the productive sector, and responds directly to the changing competence needs and qualification requirements in the labour market (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012). According to UNESCO-UNEVOC, TVET in China is legally free. Other than government funds, there are no other mechanisms to finance the TVET system. However, new regulations have been introduced that encourage the sharing of financial costs and benefits with the private sector (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012).

China's TVET system has undergone significant reforms over the last two decades. The government has set an overall vision for a "modern" TVET system that is on one hand led by the government, but works closely with the productive sector and responds directly to the changing competence needs and qualification requirements in the labour market (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012). The Chinese government has also established a comprehensive quality assurance system for TVET institutions (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2012). Chiefly, while Lesotho's TVET policy framework is focused on skills development for economic growth, China's TVET policy framework is focused on creating a "modern" TVET system that works closely with the productive sector and responds directly to changing competence needs and qualification requirements in the labour market. Lesotho could benefit from studying China's approach to improving its own TVET system.

Research Limitations

Further empirical studies are required to gauge the issues raised here from learners, instructors, policymakers and policy entrepreneurs to develop even further understanding of how these approaches work in practice to explain the results realized. There is also a greater need to understand and establish patterns using local application and implementation of policy, especially in large systems like China. Patterns to see from a theoretical standpoint, what approaches seem to result in more efficient implementation, but with a cautionary tale that not one theory can fully explain such. But more importantly, what theories of change seem to prevail better in aiding the agility to which policy changes occur. This is reversal for Lesotho.

Conclusion

In summary, we have contributed new understanding on how China built the largest TVET system. This was through review and analysis of reports, literature, and policy documents. We have made a modest, but significant contribution on how vocational education in China actually works. We have compared the education system in China as the largest, with one of the smallest, Lesotho. We drew from comparable areas on the two systems. Critically, these are two, within a small group of nations that are most competitive in labour-intensive manufacturing. China remains the number one manufacturing hub of the world. Lesotho, an incomparable country in terms of size to China, had maintained the second top-most spot in the entire African continent in textile manufacturing and exports, continues to operate kimberlite diamond mines that fetch the highest dollar per carat in the world, specializes in wool and mohair farming.

These productive industries indeed require heavy vocational skills investment. The approaches of the two countries on TVET however, couldn't have been more diverse.

Policy Implementation and Theoretical Contributions

This study has attempted to not only shed light on how these two approach vocational education policy development and implementation, but gave frame through which further empirical studies could probe what sources of change theories, if any could explain the phenomenon. For domain conservation efforts, theories surrounding studies of patterns in public policy implementation, and as stated, change theories including frontier frameworks such as the Advocacy Coalition Framework, Punctuated Equilibrium, Policy Networks and Policy Diffusion need to be followed and applied in empirical studies to further understand policy implementation, and therefore establish factorial variables that can be studied in other comparative studies. These would aid research in further understanding public policy implementation outside of systems like the World Bank's Systems Approach for Better Education Results or SABER under their Workforce Development framework.

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